

CropCare Robot: An AI-Based Autonomous Drone System for Real-Time Wheat Disease Detection

Najwa Shahbaz, Bisma Rafique, Javeria Zaheer

Faculty of Computing
Riphah International University, Islamabad, Pakistan

Abstract

Wheat farming in Pakistan still depends largely on manual field inspection for identifying crop diseases. In many cases, farmers have to walk through the field and look for visible signs on the crop. This method becomes difficult when the field is large or when the infected area is still small. Diseases such as Brown Rust, Yellow Rust, Powdery Mildew, Septoria, and other fungal infections can reduce wheat quality and yield if they are not noticed at an early stage.

In this project, we developed CropCare Robot, an AI-based autonomous drone system for wheat disease detection and crop monitoring. The system uses an ESP32-CAM module mounted on a drone to capture field images. These images are sent to a Flask backend API, where a YOLOv9 object detection model processes them for disease identification. The results are then displayed in a user-friendly application. MongoDB is used to store user data, disease detection records, image information, confidence values, and timestamps. The application also includes manual drone control, autonomous path planning, treatment recommendations, analytics, and detection history.

The system was tested using functional test cases for user login, registration, image-based disease detection, manual drone control, autonomous drone control, and detection data storage. During testing, the system was able to support crop monitoring and disease result storage, although some practical issues were observed, including Wi-Fi dependency, drone stability, and battery limitations. Overall, CropCare Robot provides a practical foundation for smart agriculture in local farming conditions.

Keywords: CropCare Robot, YOLOv9, ESP32-CAM, Wheat Disease Detection, Drone Monitoring, Flask, MongoDB, Smart Agriculture, Computer Vision, Autonomous Drone

1. Introduction

Wheat is one of the main crops grown in Pakistan and is closely linked with food security and farmer income. A large number of farmers depend on wheat production for their livelihood. However, wheat crops are often affected by diseases that reduce both yield and quality. Brown Rust, Yellow Rust, Powdery Mildew, and Septoria are common wheat diseases that can spread quickly when they are not detected at the right time.

In many farming areas, disease monitoring is still done manually. Farmers usually visit the field and inspect the crop by looking for visible symptoms on leaves and stems. This method is simple, but it is not always reliable. When the field is large, a small infected patch can easily be missed. The process also requires time, labor, and experience. If the disease is detected late, it can spread to more plants and make treatment less effective.

Technologies such as drones, computer vision, artificial intelligence, and embedded camera modules can help improve the crop monitoring process. A drone can cover more area in less time compared with manual inspection. At the same time, an AI model can analyze crop images and identify disease patterns. Object detection models such as YOLO are useful for this purpose because they can locate affected regions in images and provide fast detection results.

In this work, we implemented CropCare Robot, a drone-based monitoring system for wheat disease detection. The system uses an ESP32-CAM module to capture crop images and a YOLOv9 model to detect disease regions. A Flask backend is used to process the images and connect the model with the application. MongoDB stores user information and disease detection history. Through the application, the user can register, log in, control the drone, select monitoring areas, upload crop images, view results, receive treatment suggestions, and check monthly analytics.

The main aim of this research is to design a low-cost and user-friendly system that can reduce manual crop inspection and support early wheat disease detection.

2. Research Objectives

The main objectives of this study are:

1. To develop an autonomous drone-based monitoring system for wheat crop fields.
2. To capture real-time crop images using an ESP32-CAM module.
3. To detect wheat diseases using the YOLOv9 AI model.
4. To develop a Flask-based backend for image processing and API communication.
5. To store user and disease detection data using MongoDB.
6. To provide a user-friendly application for drone control, disease detection, treatment suggestions, and analytics.
7. To reduce manual crop inspection and improve early disease detection for farmers.

3. Related Work

Plant disease detection has been studied using image processing, machine learning, IoT-based monitoring, and agricultural robots. Earlier methods commonly used image processing techniques in which plant images were captured, cleaned, and analyzed using features such as color, shape, and texture. These approaches helped identify visible disease symptoms, but their performance often depended on lighting, image quality, and background conditions.

Machine learning and deep learning methods have improved disease detection by allowing systems to learn disease features directly from image data. Object detection models such as YOLO are useful for real-time plant disease detection because they can identify affected areas and return results quickly. This makes them suitable for applications where the system needs to process images captured from a camera or drone.

Agricultural robots and drones have also been used for crop monitoring. AGRENOBOT shows how autonomous robotic platforms can be applied in agriculture [2]. IoT-based greenhouse monitoring systems have been used to observe environmental conditions and support plant management [3]. Smart farm prototypes have also shown how IoT devices can be used for plant disease detection, diagnosis, and treatment support [4].

Most existing systems focus on crops such as tomatoes, potatoes, chilies, or greenhouse plants. Some of them require expensive hardware or complex setup, which may not be suitable for small farmers. Many systems also do not provide a simple interface for farmers, autonomous area selection, or a proper detection history. CropCare Robot was developed to address these gaps by combining ESP32-CAM image capture, YOLOv9 disease detection, Flask backend processing, MongoDB data storage, and drone-based monitoring in one application.

4. Problem Statement

Many farmers in Pakistan still inspect wheat crops manually to find disease symptoms. This process takes time and effort and is not always effective in large fields. Early disease symptoms may appear in small patches and

can be missed during field visits. Existing automated solutions are often costly, difficult to operate, or not focused on wheat disease detection in local farming conditions.

To address this issue, this research focuses on developing an AI-based autonomous drone system that captures wheat crop images, detects diseases using YOLOv9, and shows the results through an application. The system is designed to support farmers in making timely crop management decisions.

5. Proposed Methodology

The CropCare Robot system was designed using a modular approach. Each module performs a separate task, including drone movement, image capture, disease detection, backend processing, data storage, and user interaction. This structure made the system easier to develop, test, and improve during the project.

5.1 System Components

5.1.1 Drone Control Module

The drone control module handles both manual and autonomous drone movement. In manual mode, the user can control the drone through buttons such as Up, Down, Left, Right, Forward, Backward, Rotate Left, Rotate Right, and Stop All. In autonomous mode, the user can create or select a flight path, and the drone follows that path automatically. The Stop All option was included for safety during testing.

5.1.2 Image Capture Module

The ESP32-CAM module is used to capture real-time images of wheat crops. It is mounted on the drone and provides field image data for disease detection. The captured images are sent to the backend server, where they are processed by the detection model.

5.1.3 YOLOv9 Detection Module

The YOLOv9 model is used for wheat disease detection. It analyzes the crop images and identifies affected regions. The model returns the disease label, confidence score, and bounding box information for the detected area.

5.1.4 Backend Server

The backend server was developed using Python Flask. It receives images from the ESP32-CAM or from user upload, processes them through the YOLOv9 model, and sends the detection results back to the application. Flask was used because it provides a simple way to build APIs for model integration.

5.1.5 Database Module

MongoDB is used to store user information and disease detection records. The database stores registration data, disease names, confidence values, image paths or frame references, detection date and time, and result summaries. This helps users review previous detection records.

5.1.6 User Interface

The user interface provides access to all main features of the system. These include login, registration, home page, disease treatment finder, wheat disease detection, manual drone control, autonomous drone control, monthly analytics, and help page. The interface was designed to keep the workflow simple for farmers and other users.

6. System Architecture

The system architecture connects the user application, drone, ESP32-CAM, Flask backend, YOLOv9 model, and MongoDB database.

The workflow starts when the user logs into the application. After login, the user can select either disease detection or drone control. For crop monitoring, the user can upload a crop image or use the live camera stream from the ESP32-CAM. The image is then sent to the Flask backend. The YOLOv9 model processes the image and returns the disease detection result.

If a disease is detected, the application displays the result with the confidence score and treatment recommendation. The same record is stored in MongoDB for future analytics. In autonomous mode, the user selects a path, and the drone follows that path while capturing crop images.

The main architecture flow is:

8. User logs into the application.
9. User selects monitoring mode.
10. Drone captures crop images using ESP32-CAM.
11. Images are sent to Flask backend.
12. YOLOv9 model detects wheat disease.
13. Result is sent back to the application.
14. MongoDB stores detection record.
15. User views detection result, treatment recommendation, and analytics.

7. Implementation

7.1 Dataset Collection and Preprocessing

The wheat crop disease dataset was collected from Kaggle [1]. It included images of healthy and diseased wheat crops. These images were used to train the YOLOv9 model for disease detection. Disease regions were labeled using annotation tools so that the model could learn where the affected areas were located.

Before training, preprocessing and augmentation were applied to the dataset. Rotation, flipping, and contrast adjustment were used to increase image variation. This was done to help the model learn from different visual conditions and reduce dependency on one fixed image style.

7.2 Model Training

YOLOv9 was selected for disease detection because it is suitable for fast object detection tasks. The model was trained using Python. During training, the labeled dataset was loaded, parameters were configured, and the trained weights were exported for use in the Flask backend.

The trained model provides:

16. Disease class name.
17. Confidence score.
18. Bounding box around the diseased region.
19. Predicted output image.

7.3 Flask Backend Integration

A Flask-based API was developed to connect the application with the trained YOLOv9 model. The backend receives crop images, loads the trained model, performs inference, and returns the result in a structured format.

The backend performs the following tasks:

20. Receives image from user upload or ESP32-CAM.
21. Processes image using YOLOv9.
22. Generates disease prediction.
23. Sends result to frontend.
24. Stores result in MongoDB.

7.4 MongoDB Integration

MongoDB is used for user authentication and detection result storage. Each detection result is saved under the logged-in user profile. This allows users to view their own crop disease history instead of shared or mixed records.

The stored records include:

25. Disease name.
26. Confidence score.
27. Detection date and time.
28. Image or frame reference.
29. Result summary.
30. User ID.

7.5 User Authentication

The system includes registration and login modules. A new user can create an account by entering personal and location details. Existing users can log in using email and password. After successful login, the user can access the home page and other system features.

7.6 Disease Treatment Finder

The disease treatment finder allows users to enter a disease name and receive treatment recommendations. This feature was included to help farmers understand the detected disease and take suitable action after viewing the result.

7.7 Manual Drone Control

The manual drone control panel allows direct control of drone movement. The user can move the drone upward, downward, left, right, forward, backward, and rotate it. A Stop All button is included to stop drone movement immediately during testing or unsafe conditions.

7.8 Autonomous Drone Path Planning

The autonomous control module allows users to design a custom flight path. The user can add points on a grid, adjust altitude, set speed, and send the path to the drone. The drone then follows the selected path for crop monitoring.

7.9 Analytics Module

The analytics module displays monthly detection records. Each record includes the crop image, disease name, confidence score, and timestamp. This feature helps users track previous detections and identify repeated disease patterns.

8. Testing and Results

The CropCare Robot system was tested using functional test cases. Testing covered user login, registration, disease detection, manual drone control, autonomous drone control, and analytics.

8.1 User Login Testing

Login test cases were used to check whether registered users could access the system with valid credentials. The system showed an error message when invalid login details were entered. With correct credentials, the user was redirected to the home page.

8.2 User Registration Testing

Registration test cases checked whether new users could create accounts by entering valid information such as email, password, name, contact number, village, and district. The system stored the user data in the backend and redirected the user to the login screen.

8.3 Disease Detection Testing

Disease detection test cases were used to check whether users could upload wheat crop images and receive prediction results. In successful cases, the application displayed the original image, predicted image, disease result, and confidence value.

Some test cases failed when the disease was not detected correctly. These failed cases showed that the model can be improved by increasing the dataset size, improving image quality, and adding more disease variations during training.

8.4 Manual Drone Control Testing

Manual drone control was tested through movement buttons such as Up, Down, Left, Right, Rotate Right, Rotate Left, diagonal controls, Start, and Stop All. The control panel loaded successfully and responded to movement commands during testing.

8.5 Autonomous Drone Control Testing

Autonomous drone control was tested by selecting a predefined flight path and starting autonomous mode. The system checked the ESP32-CAM connection, started movement along the defined path, displayed real-time data, and saved flight and detection data.

During testing, unstable ESP32-CAM and Wi-Fi connections affected smooth operation. The system requires stable connectivity for continuous image transfer and autonomous monitoring.

8.6 System Performance

The system achieved the following outcomes:

31. Autonomous field monitoring.
32. Real-time disease detection.
33. Farmer-friendly interface.
34. Efficient data processing.
35. Disease history storage.
36. Reliable communication between major components.
37. Manual and autonomous drone control.
38. Treatment recommendation display.

Overall, the testing results show that CropCare Robot can support smart crop monitoring and AI-based wheat disease detection.

9. Challenges Faced

Several practical challenges were observed during implementation and testing.

9.1 Power and Battery Issues

The drone battery drained quickly during flight testing. To manage this issue, non-essential sensor usage was reduced, and shorter test cycles were used during experimentation.

9.2 Drone Stability in Open Fields

Wind and air pressure affected drone balance during outdoor testing. PID tuning and controlled altitude adjustments were used to improve stability.

9.3 Real-Time Streaming Delay

Live video frames created bandwidth load, which caused streaming delay. Frame-by-frame inference was used to reduce delay and make output smoother.

9.4 Dual Wi-Fi Requirement

The system required two connections at the same time: one for the ESP32-CAM hotspot and another for internet access. This created connection conflicts during testing. A mobile hotspot and secondary device setup was used to manage the drone video feed and backend communication separately.

10. Discussion

CropCare Robot combines drone monitoring, ESP32-CAM image capture, YOLOv9-based detection, Flask backend processing, MongoDB storage, and an application interface. The system was designed to be low-cost and practical for wheat crop monitoring. ESP32-CAM helped reduce hardware cost, while YOLOv9 provided image-based disease detection. Flask and MongoDB supported backend communication and detection history storage.

Compared with manual inspection, the system can reduce field-checking effort and help users identify disease symptoms earlier. The application displays results directly and also saves detection records for later review. The analytics module makes it possible to check previous detections and observe repeated disease patterns.

The system still has some limitations. Detection performance depends on the dataset, image quality, lighting, camera stability, and visibility of disease symptoms. Hardware-related issues such as drone battery timing, drone stability, and Wi-Fi connectivity also affect field performance. Even with these limitations, the system shows useful potential for small and medium-scale farms.

11. Limitations

The current system has the following limitations:

39. Stable weather conditions are required for drone flight.
40. Detection accuracy may decrease in low lighting.
41. Internet or network connectivity is needed for real-time processing.
42. Drone stability may affect image quality.
43. Battery life limits long-duration field monitoring.

44. The system currently focuses mainly on wheat diseases.
45. Wi-Fi conflicts may occur due to ESP32-CAM and backend connectivity requirements.

12. Future Work

The system can be improved in the future through the following enhancements:

46. Add multispectral and thermal cameras to detect plant stress before visible symptoms appear.
47. Add Urdu voice assistance for farmers with low reading literacy.
48. Expand the dataset for more wheat diseases.
49. Add support for other crops such as corn, rice, and sugarcane.
50. Improve drone stability and battery performance.
51. Add GPS-based field mapping.
52. Add offline disease detection support.
53. Improve live-streaming speed and reliability.
54. Add SMS or push notification alerts.
55. Add drone swarm coordination for larger fields.

13. Conclusion

This research described CropCare Robot, an AI-based autonomous drone system for real-time wheat disease detection. The system integrates ESP32-CAM for image capture, YOLOv9 for disease detection, Flask for backend processing, MongoDB for data storage, and an application interface for farmer interaction.

The system supports user authentication, image upload-based detection, live monitoring, treatment recommendations, manual drone control, autonomous path planning, and monthly analytics. Testing showed that the system can detect wheat diseases, store disease history, and support timely crop management decisions.

Although connectivity, battery life, and drone stability remain important challenges, CropCare Robot provides a practical and low-cost direction for smart agriculture. The system can help reduce manual inspection and support early disease detection in wheat farming.

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